

**STYLISTIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS RELATED TO
SPORTS**

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Abstract: *This article describes the semantic features, stylistic means of English phraseological units in sport. The purpose of the work is to study the phraseological units of a particular area of usage in sport. The objectives of the study are to identify thematic groups of phraseological units and defining their pragmatic goals in the genre of sports journalism as a kind of spontaneous public speech. Collected material can be used in linguistic and stylistic analysis of texts of various styles and genres.*

Keywords: *Stylistic means, phraseological unit, stylistic device, literary text, connotative, discourse, extralinguistic, phrasemes, idioms, semantic area, semantic field, sports reporting, sports journalism.*

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INTRODUCTION

Just as the study of phraseological and stylistic problems plays an important role in the translation of linguistic and literary texts, today the study of specific aspects of linguistics, in particular, in terms of terminological systems, is also relevant. "The study of the relationship between terminology and phraseology is one of the new, as well as topical issues of modern linguistics¹".

Since there is an integral connection between the terminology of physical education and sports in English and the general literary language, universal lexical-semantic processes are observed in the terminological system. While most of the terms that have passed from sports terminology to general use continue to be expressed in their original form without changing their form, it is also observed that some terms are used in new meanings. Terminological units with such a stylistic color, of course, create some difficulties in the translation of field terms, in their interpretation. In general, phraseological and stylistic units in linguistics are semantically and structurally expressive-emotional, functional-stylistic, connotative, so translating in accordance with the norms of this or that language is a very complex and responsible task. This does not bypass the terminological system either. Such phraseological and stylistic units are reflected in communication as portable and descriptive means of speech, which is explained by their complexity in lexical-semantic, pragmatic and structural aspects. Another important aspect of phraseology in sports is that they are not literally translated from

¹ Usmonov S. Some issues of Uzbek terminology. – Toshkent, 1968. P. 148.

one language to another. The meaning of phraseologies does not depend on the primary meaning of the words involved as structural units².

METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS

In the process of this research, we collected phrases, idioms and stylistic devices in the field of sports literature, newspapers and magazines, and TV shows from English-speaking foreign countries. It is worth nothing that we have found and analyzed expressions in the field of sports by A.V. Kunin's book "Anglo-Russian Phraseological Dictionary" (1984) and A. H. Блеер, ф. П. Суслов, д. А. Тышлер "Терминология спорта толковый словарь-справочник более 10 000 терминов" (2010). In addition, "Explanatory dictionary of Russian-Uzbek terms of physical culture and sports" (1961), published by R. Ismailov and M. Norkin, N. Tursunov's "Anglo-Russian dictionary of sports terms" (2005), Y. Khamroeva's "Dictionary of Uzbek language Explanatory dictionary of self-explanatory words" (2007), "Uzbek-Russian-English dictionary of sports terms" and "English-Uzbek-Russian dictionary of sports terms" (2015) published by H. Rafiev, Sh. Butaev were involved in the research analysis. PhD. Sarimsokov KH.A. "Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида спорт терминларининг чоғиштирма тадқиқи" (2020) and PhD. Kuldashova N.B. "Француз ва ўзбек тилларида спорт терминологиясининг миллий-маданий хусусиятлари" (2020).

Phraseology is a well-studied linguistic discipline. The theoretical and methodological basis of the paper is comprised of the works of A.N. Baranov, V.V. Vinogradov, D.O. Dobrovolsky, V.P. Zhukov, V.M. Mokienko, V.N. Teliya, A.I. Fedorov. We will rely on the narrow understanding of phraseological units, which defines them as units that are characterized by "idiomaticity, expressiveness, stability, reproducibility, imagery, nominative function³".

Phraseologists emphasize that a phraseological unit "never arises immediately, at the very first moment of creation and use of its material composition", it is "always the result of gradual formation⁴".

Ch. Bally's theory which states that the main feature of a phraseological unit is possibility or impossibility to replace it by one single word⁵.

The concept of phraseological unit has been first used by Charles Bally, wherefrom it was taken by V.V. Vinogradov and other Soviet linguists, who translated it by "frazеологическая единица". He defines them as ready-made language units that are taken from one generation to another and are used in the process of speech as traditional word combinations. Shansky defines phraseologisms as "frozen patterns of language that consist of two or more components and allow little or no variation in form, structure or meaning⁶".

RESULTS

² Akobirov F. Lexicographic development of terminology in bilingual dictionaries. Abstract of the thesis. diss. ... Cand. philol. Sciences. – Tashkent, Author. diss. ... Cand. philol. sciences. – Tashkent, 1969. P. 25.

³ Рычкова Н. Г. Синтаксические механизмы формирования экспрессивности (на примере предложений с русскими глагольными фразеологизмами с прототипической структурой перемещения): Дис. канд. филол. наук. – Новосибирск, 2017. С. 413.

⁴ Амосова Н.Н. Основы английской фразеологии. – Ленинград: ЛГУ, 1963. С. 360.

⁵ Кунин А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка. Издание второе. – М., 1996. С. 43.

⁶ Кунин А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка. Издание второе. – М., 1996. С. 46.

In fact, in the connotative semantics of phraseological units related to sports, there are features and professional prototypes related to human activity and character. Sports brought many new concepts and terms into the vocabulary of the Uzbek language and others.

“Sports commentators try to do everything possible so that the viewer (or listener) becomes not only interested in the report but also experiences emotional stress⁷”. This emotional background is characteristic of sports broadcasts. In order to ensure a high level of emotionality, commentators use phraseological units in their speech. The use of phraseological units enables excluding excessive formality and monotony of sports reports. Sports presenters on television use the phraseological diversity of the Russian language in their speech as a source of expression and emotional involvement, which is almost obligatory for sports reports⁸.

To be more precise, such professional prototypes are an inspiring force that reveals the inner abilities of athletes, moves them to victory. In many sources, units of portable meaning are referred to as phraseological units. Such prototypes, which are present in the internal lexical-semantic, cognitive properties of phraseological units, are the main source in the formation of connotation. According to V.M. Mokienko, who specifically studied the emotive-expressive nature of phraseological units, “Like other languages, English and Russian have impressive, figurative phraseological units. In order to achieve adequacy in their translation, it is necessary to correctly understand whether the phraseology in each language is used in a figurative or fixed sense. Otherwise, the meaning of phraseological units (PHUs) may change completely or be misinterpreted. To do this, it is first necessary to determine the original content of PHUs in the context or to use special phraseological dictionaries. Because they have portable, connotative meanings, their interpretation and content cannot be found in ordinary dictionaries⁹”.

It is known that in linguistic sources phraseological units are divided into three types: a) phraseological integrity; b) phraseological compounds; c) phraseological confusions (idioms). Phrases in which one word is lexically and semantically correct and the other is used in a figurative sense are called phraseological compounds. For example: to relax (rest - in the literal sense, to take out - in the figurative sense) or to be exhausted (without - in the literal sense, to be exhausted - in the figurative sense). When the meanings and grammatical aspects of the words in a sentence are combined, phrases that give a common portable meaning are called phraseological units. For example: to pull the heart behind (fear), to lift to the sky (praise). Phraseologisms that do not have any lexical connection between the meanings of the words in them and the meanings of the expressions are called phraseological confusions. For example: if it falls into the mill, the whole exit, pressing the iron in the heat, taking the mouse's nest for a thousand coins, and so on.

⁷ Куранова Т. П. Метафора как средство создания выразительности в дискурсе телевизионного спортивного репортажа. – Ярославль: РИО ЯГПУ, 2018. С. 111-116.

⁸ Куранова Т. П. Фразеология спортивных репортажей: семантические и прагматические особенности / Т. П.

Куранова // Верхневолжский филологический вестник. – 2019. С. 60-68.

⁹ Mokienko V.M. Riddles of Russian phraseology. – St. Petersburg: Avalon, 2005. P. 19.

ANALYSIS

Phraseologisms are usually formed on the basis of free word combinations in a language. However, they acquire a portable meaning and are absorbed into the language as a result of their components being combined and applied as a whole. Some types of phraseology also reflect national traditions. When translating them from one language to another, it is advisable to use their alternatives without literally translating the components of the phrase¹⁰.

Classifications of phraseological units:

A.J.Smirnitsky classifies phraseological units according to their stylistic features:

- a) phraseological units (stylistically neutral, with faded metaphorical motivation, e.g., be in love, fall in love);
- b) idioms (they are based on metaphor, they are emotionally and stylistically coloured, e.g., cool as a cucumber)¹¹.

Another classification in which there are two principles applied is established by N.Amosova. She distinguishes two types of phraseological units:

- a) phrasemes (units of fixed context in which one of the components has specialized meaning dependent on the second component, e.g., small talk, fair sex);
- b) idioms (idioms are semantically and grammatically inseparable units, e.g., play with fire)¹².

Taking into account the comparative analysis of different classifications of phraseological units which the author has observed, she has to admit that the following classification worked out by A.V. Kunin can be considered the most detailed one. He has critically examined most of the existing classifications and elaborated his own classification of phraseological units which is based on more thorough analysis of these phenomena of language. In his classification A.V. Kunin keeps a close watch to the elements of phraseology which have not been emphasized by other researchers, as well as takes into consideration also the development of the English language. Since A.V. Kunin's classification of phraseological units is grounded on wide theoretical and practical material concerning different languages, the author of the present article assumes that this classification could be applied also to the phraseological systems of other languages.

Kunin has worked out a structural-semantic classification, which reveals the function of a phraseological unit depending on its size (collocations or sentences).

DISCUSSION

The use of sports-related phraseological units in oral and written communication is widespread in the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, and other English-speaking countries. One of the main reasons for this is the popularity of sports competitions among the peoples of the world, and the other is explained by the socio-political influence of Britain on the colonial states under its control. Today, the United Kingdom and the United States continue to lead in all areas, especially in sports. In this sense, we see that the origin of some sports

¹⁰ Marchand H. The Categories and Types of Present-Day English Word-formation. – München: C.H. Beck'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung, 1969. P. 26-218.

¹¹ Smirnitsky A.I. Lexicology of the English Language. – Moscow, 1956. P. 125.

¹² Амосова Н.Н. Основы английской фразеологии. – Ленинград: ЛГУ, 1963. С. 360.

(football, cricket, rugby, basketball, baseball, hockey, golf, boxing, American football) is associated with these countries.

Although these phraseological expressions are not small in number, they have allowed us to identify and explain lexical-semantic, structure-functional features of English-language sports terms. During the course of the research, phraseological units can be categorized into several types of sports, which are noted in modern English, as well as in sports.

1. The phraseological units which are directly related to show etymology of physical education and sport. For example: *Shoot the ball into one's own goal* - score the ball into own goal (football). *Get to first base* – the first step towards success, the first step (baseball). *Hit below the belt* – to hit the lower part of the belt, using the trick (boxing)¹³.

2. The phraseological units which are indirectly related to show etymology of physical education and sport. For example: *Also ran* – loser, participant in sports contests who failed in the competitions. Example, English: *I'm afraid he'll always be one of life's rans* – Uzbek translation: Афсуски, унинг ҳеч қачон иши юришмайди (омади чопмайди) – Russian: Я боюсь, что он всегда будет неудачником¹⁴.

3. In the third group we collected phraseological unit that “Half parts belongs Sport sphere”. With such phraseological units, no idea about the etymology and origin of sports types. The majority of these are not just sports compound words today, but also the combined lexemes in the social, military, navy, and empty fields. Examples: *To catch the card* – to fish, to dive deep; *head to head* – to fight hard and with courage (english: the governor and the senator went head to head in a spontaneous debate – uzbek translation: губернатор ва сенатор режалаштирилмаган мунозара (дебат)да матонат билан кураш олиб борди, охиригача курашмоқ, “ё ҳаёт ё мамот” шиори остида курашмоқ; *to win hands down* – to win easily (english: The other team are two men short, in theory, at least, we ought to win hands down – uzbek translation: Бошқа жамоаларда икки ўйинчи етишмаяпти, биз уларни *осонликча ютиш* эҳтимолимиз бор. – russian; У другой команды не хватает двух игроков. По всей вероятности, мы должны легко выиграть)¹⁵.

The use of phraseological units in oral and written discourses is shaped by specific extralegalistic factors, that are, interactions with specific sports, sporting events and events that reflect specific situations and events.

Although the lexical units that make up the phraseological expressions are free lexemes separately, they are portable when translated from one language to another, and it is advisable to find and translate their alternatives. There are also such expressions in the English language as in the field of physical culture and sports, which may be said to have been formed by the combination of other words in the same word.

We also observe that some of them have polysemantic properties.

Consolation race – 1) *horse racing* – от чоптириш мусобақаси (пойгаси), 2) *participant (lost) in previous competition* – олдинги мусобақада мағлуб бўлган (ютқазган)

¹³ Кунин А. В. Англо-русский фразеологический словарь. Издание 4-е. – М.: 1984. С. 944.

¹⁴ Кунин А. В. Англо-русский фразеологический словарь. Издание 4-е. – М.: 1984. С. 944.

¹⁵ Кунин А. В. Англо-русский фразеологический словарь. Издание 4-е. – М.: 1984. С. 944.

иштирокчи, 3) *horseback riding* – эрмакка айланиб келиш (отда); *consolation prize* – reward – таскин, тасалли учун берилган мукофот, соврин (*two hundred runners-up will get a consolation prize* – prizes will also be awarded to the second place winners – иккинчи ўринни эгаллаганларга ҳам соврин берилади); *consolation heat* – test running, run a race – синов тариқасида белгили масофага югуриш, чопиш; *consolation goal* – impressive goal – таъсирли гол. To date, the problem of classification and characterization of phraseological units, and their comparative scientific analysis, remains one of the most important tasks of modern phraseology.

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